

Republic of the Philippines

HOUSE OF REPRESENTATIVES

Quezon City, Metro Manila

SENATE

Pasay City, Metro Manila

TWENTIETH CONGRESS

First Regular Session

HOUSE BILL NO. _____

SENATE BILL NO. _____

Introduced by Jonelle Peter C. Muñoz (*Citizen of the Republic*)

AN ACT

SETTING MINIMUM GOOD GOVERNANCE MEMBERSHIP REQUIREMENTS FOR LOCAL CHIEF EXECUTIVES SUCH AS MAYOR AND GOVERNOR

SECTION 1. Short Title

This Act shall be known as the “**Good Governance Membership Requirements Act for Local Chief Executives such as Mayor and Governor**”.

SECTION 2. Declaration of Policy

It is hereby declared the policy of the State to promote transparency, accountability, and ethical governance among all public officials, particularly Local Chief Executives. This Act establishes minimum good governance standards that every Mayor and Governor shall uphold and implement during their term of office, as a demonstration of integrity, public trust, and commitment to genuine service to the Filipino people.

SECTION 3. Freedom of Information and Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinances

All Local Chief Executives shall prioritize the passage and implementation of the following ordinances within one (1) year from the start of their term:

- *Freedom of Information (FOI) Ordinance*, comparable in quality to that of Pasig City, including a penalty clause for non-compliance; and

- *Anti-Political Dynasty Ordinance*, to prevent the concentration of political power within families and promote equal opportunity in public service.

SECTION 4. Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth (SALN)

Every Local Chief Executive shall ensure that their Statement of Assets, Liabilities, and Net Worth (SALN) is publicly available from the first year of public service up to the present, if incumbent. Such SALNs shall be accessible in accordance with existing laws and regulations. Sensitive information protected under the Data Privacy Act may be redacted, provided that transparency and accountability are not compromised.

SECTION 5. Bank Secrecy Waiver

Each Local Chief Executive shall execute a bank secrecy waiver authorizing the Office of the Ombudsman to access their bank records for official investigation purposes. The waiver may be made public at the discretion of the official, provided that it does not compromise ongoing investigations or result in political misuse.

SECTION 6. Education and Development Requirements

- a. *No School Backlog*. All Local Chief Executives shall ensure that there is no school backlog at any level from Kindergarten to Grade 12 and up to college, as certified by the Department of Education (DepEd) and the Commission on Higher Education (CHED).
- b. *Adequate Schools for OSYA*. After ensuring compliance with Section 6a, the city, municipality, or province under the Local Chief Executive shall provide adequate schools and learning facilities proportionate to the number of Out-of-School Youth and Adults (OSYA) within its jurisdiction.
- c. *Free College Tuition and Stipend*. All Local Chief Executives shall ensure free college tuition fees and provide a stipend allowance of Five Thousand Pesos (₱5,000) per semester to students whose families have a household income of less than Ten Thousand Pesos (₱10,000) per month.

SECTION 7. Health and Medical Services Requirements

- a. *No Hospital Bed Backlog*. All Local Chief Executives shall ensure that there is no hospital bed backlog in public hospitals within their jurisdiction, as certified by the Department of Health (DOH).
- b. *Adequate Medical Specialists*. After ensuring compliance with Section 7a, all Local Chief Executive shall provide an adequate number of medical specialists,

including but not limited to heart specialists, brain specialists, and other critical care professionals, to address the health needs of their constituents. Emergency patients shall not wait more than four (4) hours for life-saving procedures or surgeries.

- c. *Free Hospital Care for Low-Income Families.* All Local Chief Executives shall ensure free hospital medicines, surgeries, and other medical services for families with a household income of less than Ten Thousand Pesos (₱10,000) per month. For other patients who have been employed for at least twelve (12) months and whose salary exceeds Ten Thousand Pesos (₱10,000) per month, the maximum hospital bill shall not exceed one month's salary of the highest income-earning member of the family.

SECTION 8. Transparency and Accountability Measures

Public Ledger of Contracts and Documents. All Local Chief Executives shall maintain a public ledger of all contracts, agreements, and official documents signed or executed in the performance of their duties, accessible to the public.

Transparent Local Website. All Local Chief Executives shall maintain a transparent and accessible local government website, modeled after best practices such as Singapore, which shall include:

- All legislative measures, ordinances, and resolutions;
- Official reports and public documents; and
- Other public documents required by law to be posted publicly.

SECTION 9. Financial Accountability and Audit Compliance

The local government under a Local Chief Executive must maintain the highest standards of financial management and accountability. To ensure compliance:

- a. *Internal Controls and Reporting.* The Local Chief Executive shall establish and maintain proper internal controls over all financial transactions, ensure timely submission of financial reports, and monitor subordinate offices to prevent irregularities and mismanagement.
- b. *Audit Compliance Incentives.* The local government is encouraged to maintain exemplary financial performance, as reflected in the annual Commission on Audit (COA) examination. Local Chief Executives whose local governments receive no Notices of Disallowances (NOD), Notices of Charge (NOC), or Notices of Suspension (NOS) during the audit may be eligible for recognition or incentives, subject to COA certification.

- c. *Limits on Penalties.* No administrative penalties shall be imposed on a Local Chief Executive for audit findings beyond their direct control, such as delays in reports from subordinate offices or unforeseen disbursement issues. Penalties shall only apply to failures that are within the LCE's direct responsibility, such as deliberate mismanagement, neglect in implementing internal controls, or refusal to comply with reporting requirements.

SECTION 10. Full-Time Service Ordinance

All elective officials under the Local Chief Executive *shall render full-time service from 8:00 a.m. to 5:00 p.m., five days a week*, similar to ordinary government employees. Each city, municipality, or province shall enact an ordinance to implement and enforce this requirement.

SECTION 11. Monthly Public Forum

Every Local Chief Executive shall conduct at least one *public forum* per month, lasting not less than *two (2) hours*, to engage constituents, promote transparency, and gather feedback on governance and public service initiatives.

The public forum shall be open to everyone and must include representatives from diverse sectors, including at least one teacher, one student, one member of a civil society organization, one engineer, one architect, one lawyer, one accountant, one IT professional, one unemployed person, one philosopher, one businessperson, and one public policymaker.

The time and venue of the forum must be made public at least one week before the scheduled forum.

SECTION 12. Notarized Transcript of Official Meetings

All meetings related to the duties and responsibilities of the Local Chief Executive shall have *notarized transcripts or certified minutes*, which shall be made *accessible on the local government website*, ensuring that decisions are made in the best interest of the people and the greater good.

SECTION 13. Penalties for Non-Compliance

Any Local Chief Executive who fails to comply with the provisions of this Act shall be subject to the following administrative penalties, without prejudice to other penalties under existing laws:

1. *First offense*: Written warning and public notice of non-compliance;
2. *Second offense*: Fine equivalent to one month's salary, to be remitted to the DepEd or CHED for providing scholarships to qualified students;
3. *Third offense*: Fine equivalent to one year's salary, to be remitted to the DepEd or CHED for providing scholarships to qualified students;
4. *Fourth offense*: Suspension from office for thirty (30) days, accompanied by a written explanation letter detailing the reasons for non-compliance and a plan to implement the provisions within the next twelve (12) months;
5. *Fifth offense and subsequent offenses*: Suspension from office for six (6) months and referral to the Ombudsman for possible administrative sanctions due to neglect of duties and responsibilities.

During the suspension, the Local Chief Executive shall be temporarily replaced by the Vice Mayor or Vice Governor, as applicable.

SECTION 14. Separability Clause

If any provision of this Act is held invalid or unconstitutional, no other provision shall be affected thereby.

SECTION 15. Effectivity

This Act shall take effect upon its approval.

Approved: _____

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Written for Filipino children deprived of education and a better future
because of corruption and greed.